

REVIEW

GEOLOGY AND HYDROGEOLOGY DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES BETWEEN QUICKSAND AND WETLAND: A SHORT REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The major difference between quick sand and wetland has been a major contest in term of basis difference and has made the usage of the two interchangeable. In this short review, the basic differences, similarities and their formation are clearly stated. More so, the geology and the hydrogeology of the two terms were also stated

KEYWORDS: Quicksand, wetland, geology, ecosystem

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INTRODUCTION

Geology is the science comprising the study of solid earth, the rocks of which it is composed, and the processes by which they change. Geology can also refer generally to the study of the solid features of any celestial body (such as the geology of the Moon or Mars).Geology gives insight into the history of the earth, as it provides the primary evidence for plate tectonics, the evolutionary history of life and past climates. In modern times, geology is commercially important for mineral and hydrocarbon exploration and exploitation and for evaluating water resources (Bell; 1983).

What is Hydrogeology

Hydrogeology (*hydro-* meaning water, and *-geology* meaning the study of the earth) is the area of geology that deals with the distribution and movement of ground water in the soil and rocks of the Earth's crust (commonly in aquifers). The term geo-hydrology is often used interchangeably. Some make the minor distinction between a hydrologist or engineer applying them to geology (geo-hydrology), and a geologist applying them to hydrology (hydrogeology) (Obiefuna and Nur, 2003; Obiefuna et al 2010)

What is Wetland

A wetland is "an ecosystem that arises when inundation by water produces soils dominated by anaerobic processes, which, in turn, forces the biota, particularly rooted plants, to adapt to flooding (4). There are four main kinds of wetlands – marsh, swamp, bog and fen (bogs and fens both being types of mires). Some experts also recognize wet meadows and aquatic ecosystems as additional wetland types (Fraser and Keddy, 2005). The largest wetlands in the world include the swamp forests of the Amazon and the peat lands of Siberia (Ghabo, 2007). It is a land area that is saturated with water, either permanently or seasonally, such that it takes on the characteristics of a distinct ecosystem (MacKenzie and Moran, 2004). Primarily, the factor that distinguishes wetlands from other land forms or water bodies is the characteristic vegetation that is adapted to its unique soil conditions: Wetlands consist primarily of hydric soil, which supports aquatic plants (Maltby and Barker, 2009).

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The water found in wetlands can be saltwater, freshwater, or brackish (MacKenzie and Moran, 2004). Main wetland types include swamps, marshes, bogs and fen (MacKenzie and Moran, 2004; Maltby and Barker, 2009). Sub-types include mangrove, Carr, pocosin, and varzea. The largest wetlands in the world include the Amazon River basin and the West Siberian Plain (Mitsch et al., 2009) Another large wetland is the pantanal, which straddles Brazil, Bolivia and Paraguay in South America

Wetlands vary widely due to local and regional differences in topography, hydrology vegetation, and other factors, including human involvement. Wetlands can be divided into two main classes: tidal and non-tidal areas.

Types of wetland

A. Marine and Coastal Zone wetlands

(a) Marine waters—permanent shallow waters less than six meters deep at low tide; includes sea bays, straits, (b) Sub tidal aquatic beds; includes kelp beds, sea grasses, tropical marine meadows, (c) Coral reefs, (d) Rocky marine shores; includes rocky offshore islands, sea cliffs, (e) Sand, shingle or pebble beach's; includes sand bars, spits, sandy islets

B. Inland wetlands

(a). Permanent rivers and streams; includes waterfalls, (b). Seasonal and irregular rivers and streams, (c). Inland deltas (permanent), (d). Riverine floodplains; includes river flats, flooded river basins, seasonally flooded grassland, savanna and palm savanna, (e). Permanent freshwater lakes (> 8 ha); includes large oxbow lakes

C. Human-made wetlands

(a). Water storage areas; reservoirs, barrages, hydro-electric dams, impoundments (generally > 8 ha), (b). Ponds, including farm ponds, stock ponds, small tanks (generally < 8 ha), (c). Aquaculture ponds; fish ponds, shrimp ponds, (d). Salt exploitation; salt pans, saline, e. Excavations; gravel pits, borrow pits, mining pools, (f). Wastewater treatment; sewage farms, settling ponds, oxidation basins, (g). Irrigated land and irrigation channels; rice fields, canals, ditches

What is quicksand

Quicksand is a colloid hydrogel consisting of fine granular material (such as sand or silt), clay, and water. When water in the sand cannot escape, it creates liquefied soil that loses strength and cannot support weight. Quicksand can be formed in standing water or in upwards flowing water (as from an artesian spring). In the case of upwards flowing water, seepage forces oppose the force of gravity and suspend the soil particles.

Quicksand is an interesting natural phenomenon -- it is actually solid ground that has been liquefied by a saturation of water. The "quick" refers to how easily the sand shifts when in this semiliquid state. It is not a unique type of soil; it is usually just sand or another type of grainy soil. Quicksand is nothing more than a soupy mixture of sand and water. It can occur anywhere under the right conditions, according to (Maltby and Barker, 2009; Mitsch et al., 2009).

The saturated sediment may appear quite solid until a sudden change in pressure or shock initiates liquefaction. This causes the sand to form a suspension and lose strength. The cushioning of water gives quicksand, and other liquefied sediments, a spongy, fluid like texture. Objects in liquefied sand sink to the level at which the weight of the object is equal to the weight of the displaced soil/water mix and the submerged object floats due to its buoyancy.

Liquefaction is a special case of quicksand. In this case, sudden earthquake forces immediately increases the pore pressure of shallow groundwater. The saturated liquefied soil loses strength, causing buildings or other objects on that surface to sink or fall over.

Properties of Quicksand

Quicksand is a non-Newtonian fluid: when undisturbed, it often appears to be solid ("gel" form), but a minor (less than 1%) change in the stress on the quicksand will cause a sudden decrease in its viscosity ("sol" form). After an

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initial disturbance, such as a person attempting to walk on it, the water and sand in the quicksand separate and dense regions of sand sediment form; it is because of the formation of these high volume fraction regions that the viscosity of the quicksand seems to decrease suddenly. Someone stepping on it will start to sink. To move within the quicksand, a person or object must apply sufficient pressure on the compacted sand to re-introduce enough water to liquefy it. The forces required to do this are quite large: to remove a foot from quicksand at a speed of .01 m/s would require the same amount of force as "that needed to lift a medium-sized car (Mitsch *et al.*, 2009). Because of the higher density of the quicksand, it would be impossible for a human or animal to completely sink in the quicksand, though natural hazards present around the quicksand would lead people to believe that quicksand is dangerous. In actuality the quicksand is harmless on its own, but because it greatly impedes human locomotion, the quicksand would allow harsher elements like solar radiation, dehydration, carnivores, hypothermia or tides to harm a trapped person (Fraser and Keddy, 2005; Mitsch *et al.*, 2009). However, the way to escape is to wiggle the legs as slowly as possible in order to reduce viscosity, to try spreading the arms and legs far apart and lying supine to increase the body's surface area, which should allow one to float

Quicksand Composition

Quicksand is sand saturated with water and also has an upward current. The pressure of water and current keeps the grains of sand from having any friction, and the result is a fine, quicksand can't support a lot of weight. Water comes in from the bottom of this gooey mess, so the top appears dry and the quicksand is hidden from view. Quicksand is not as dangerous as the movies portray (Mitsch *et al.*, 2009). Quicksand is often only a few feet deep, and even if you do sink into it, the human body can float in quicksand just like water. Quicksand is created when water saturates an area of loose sand and the ordinary sand is agitated. When the water trapped in the batch of sand can't escape, it creates liquefied soil that can no longer support weight. There are two ways in which sand can become agitated enough to create quicksand according to researcher (Johnson *et al.*, 2005).

a. Flowing underground water - The force of the upward water flow opposes the force of gravity, causing the granules of sand to be more buoyant.

b. Earthquakes - The force of the shaking ground can increase the pressure of shallow groundwater, which liquefies sand and silt deposits. The liquefied surface loses strength, causing buildings or other objects on that surface to sink or fall over (Brix, 1993). Vibration tends to enhance the quickness, so what is reasonably solid initially may become soft and then quick, according to researchers (Vymazal and Kröpfleova, 2008). The vibration plus the water barrier reduces the friction between the sand particles and causes the sand to behave like a liquid. To understand quicksand, you have to understand the process of liquefaction. When soil liquefies, as with quicksand, it loses strength and behaves like a viscous liquid rather than a solid, according to the Utah Geological Survey 1998. Liquefaction can cause buildings to sink significantly during earthquakes.

While quicksand can occur in almost any location where water is present, there are certain locations where it's more prevalent. Places where quicksand is most likely to occur include: riverbanks, beaches, lake shorelines, near underground springs and marshes

The similarities between wetland and Quicksand:

Wetland and quicksand have a few features in common. Both are soft, porous types of earth. Both of these natural land formations are found in areas where water is plentiful and drainage is poor. Wetland is an ecosystem within itself. Quicksand is found in warmer climates that contain deserts and sand, and unlike wetland, it is considered dangerous (Bell, 2005; Maltby and Barker, 2009).

The Differences Between wetland and Quicksand:

Wetland systems naturally produce an array of vegetation and other ecological products that can be harvested for personal and commercial use. The most significant of these is fish which have all or parts of their life-cycle occur within a wetland system. Fresh and saltwater fish are the main source of protein for one billion people and comprise 15% of an additional two billion people's diets. In addition, fish generate a fishing industry that provides 80% of the income and employment to residents in developing countries. Another food staple found in wetland systems is rice,

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a popular grain that is consumed at the rate of 1/5 of the total global calorie count. In Bangladesh, Cambodia and Vietnam, where rice paddies are predominant on the landscape, rice consumption reach 70%. But in quicksand, production of any array or ecological product cannot take place because of the nature of the area. Many species in wetland systems are unique due to the long period of time that the ecosystem has been physically isolated from other aquatic sources. Multiple small mammals as well as large herbivore and apex species such as the Florida Panther live within and around wetlands. The wetland ecosystem attracts mammals due to its prominent seed sources, invertebrate populations, and numbers of small reptiles and amphibians such as fish, frog, snakes, lizards, goannas and turtles (Maltby and Barker, 2009).

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